

The Imaginary and the Pandemic

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Introduction

Throughout the 20th century, the imaginary was a topic of interest to authors such as Gaston Bachelard, Sigmund Freud, Gilbert Durand, Michel Maffesoli, Jacques Lacan, Cornelius Castoriadis, Paul Ricoeur and Henri Corbin, among others.

These theorists presented different dimensions and meanings to the imaginary, establishing it as the set of imaginative attitudes that result in the production and reproduction of symbols, images, myths and archetypes by the human being (Durand), as the heritage of a group (Maffesoli) or even when giving new names, like mundus imaginalis (Corbin), to differentiate it from the common sense.

In the field of Psychoanalysis, the imaginary was the object of reflection by Freud and Lacan.

For the former, normal life takes place at the level of manifest content. The level of latent content is the real and hidden unconscious content, which is hidden under the manifest content. Therefore, the imaginary refers to the ego, the self.

Lacan, on the other hand, when delimiting the register of the imaginary (1936 to 1953), emphasizes the importance of the other for the affirmation of identity in the constitution of the self.

In other words, "the other is our measure". It is the place of identifications and dual relationships.

In the universe of the psychoanalyst's ideas and thought, "the advance of the conceptualization of the self was a consequence of the changes that they suffered in the course of his work, the notions of object and fantasy" (LEITE, 2008. s / r). "The self, classically defined as the seat of the perception-consciousness function, when taken up by Lacan, appears as an object proper to man, whose particularity is a relationship with the signifier

For Lacan, three are the conceptual categories of human reality:

- 1) Imaginary - theater of the illusions of the self, roles of an individual;
- 2) Real - an excess that cannot be symbolized - which cannot be symbolized;
- 3) Symbol - "as being the ideal of the self, which would determine and sustain the imaginary projection on the ideal self" fact that Lacan (1953) establishes narcissism as

the center of his theory of the imaginary: "it is for narcissism - as the primordial moment in the constitution of the 'I' by images - that it turns to the theorization built about the mirror stage also recalls Lacanian records, when he says he is the ego servant and master of the imaginary, who it is projected in the images in which it is mirrored: imaginary of nature, of the body, of the mind, of social relations.

Searching for itself, the ego believes it is in the mirror of creatures to get lost in what is not him. This situation is fundamentally mythical. A metaphor of the human condition, since we are always longing for a completeness that can never be found, infinitely captured in mirages that rehearse senses where meaning is always lacking.

Thinkers from other fields of knowledge studied the imaginary showing that its dimension goes beyond the unreal and the fictitious.

Social imaginary

I

Social contexts are defined by the multiplicity of interactions and exchanges between the people that comprise it, giving rise to different understandings of realities, knowledge, ideologies, conceptions of life and cultural practices, leading to the interpretation of multiple historical, political events, social, educational and community life, given through dissent or consensus; what has allowed people's access to knowledge, to the economy, to education, to health, to the understanding of policies, to technologies and, in general, to the goods of culture, hence the formulation of policies public, which seek equity for access to these goods and services, which although worth mentioning have focused on recognizing historically segregated and discriminated populations.

From different perspectives have been defined in the international, national and district framework, social concepts and imaginary about social relations, mediated by the knowledge of the same society, which implies the recognition that the participation of all people in a framework of equality and equalization of opportunities for the enhancement of human development and the guarantee of access to cultural produce.

It is worth mentioning that when mentioning equal opportunities, it is built from the legal and participatory framework so that all Rights, cultural assets, are effectively accessed; since the diverse understandings and interpretations are constructed as social imageries that define and interpret the social, environmental, ideological, biological, political, educational characteristics among others, which have perpetuated in the establishment of revealing the differences, not as opportunities for celebration

and recognition but as a means to divide, classify and frame populations; generating barriers, limits and gaps for access to cultural assets, rights and participation in different scenarios.

The division of society into sectors and social classes has generated patterns of violence in historical moments with different social groups, which due to the relationship with the social imaginary as a construct, were accepted in society, leading to practices of segregation and discrimination such as In a naturalized way, this has led to the formulation of policies that seek to guide the activities of the different governments within the framework of the commitment to the integral development of all people. These policies have been generated at the international, national and district levels.

II

To a certain extent the imaginary it is impregnated in the forms of the social system, where it could develop and also in the subjective production that individuals carry out, who are responsible for building new imaginary; In the end, the social system already has an established structure, however, it is susceptible to modifications and therefore modifications of existing social imagery.

The union between individual and social systems would be given by the social imaginary, which would function as a transversal mechanism, regardless of the vertex that is considered as the starting point of reality, since the nuclear mass of reality is made up of the imaginary, which gives it sustenance.

The field of action and intervention of the imaginary is holistic, constituting itself as one of the most far-reaching sociological elements, not in its specific forms, but in its operation.

Given that they would exist at all times and in all places, we could say that in all societal spheres there is the presence of social imagery, this is the basis of their power and the value of having a mechanism that can be associated with any manifestation of reality.

In this perspective, the social imaginary, rather than a process or a mechanism for constructing reality, is reality constructed, legitimized or to be legitimized.

The imaginary is the product of a process of construction and maintenance in society from a series of communicative and meaningful interactions (intersubjective).

It is constituted as a process in balance between both bases, given that without the intervention of the creative action of individuals and without reproduction and maintenance through established and differentiated systems, the imaginary would not exist.

The imaginary it is a conjunction of systems and subjects, where it is not possible without one or the other, both elements are protagonists.

The social imaginary it is a meta-significant construct that brings together elements from a group of subjects (or even a single individual), from a system that validates it, from the social networks that are established, legitimize it, and its reproduction , circulation and scope.

III

The imaginary alludes to a process of socio-cultural construction that throughout history has been transformed responding to social needs, in the course of this time the imaginary has been configured or defined, from various perspectives, for example that the imaginary It is found in the field of the unreal or what does not respond to the truth.

It can be classified as:

- Representation that is not subject to a certain purpose, but is instituted in society, Ideology, is considered as a pragmatic discourse linked to an institution, political or religious Imagery, a set of images that by themselves do not make up an imaginary
- Mentality, a way of reacting before the world and a determined society, it constitutes the meeting point for ways of thinking, feeling and acting;
- Symbolic, set of objects and metaphorical practices;
- Collective memory, memory of past things, stories and narrations;

The term Imaginary has gone through multiple definitions and depending on the authors, it is relegated to an investigative process that is specifically responsible for understanding why certain practices are accepted within the collective, and how they are perpetuated or transformed into the passage of historical moments.

The concept of imaginary within an Ideational system that contemplates ideologies, representation and the imaginary, which is defined as a system of social beliefs, nourished by visions, discourse and social context that responds to the different conceptions of the world and of knowledge.

1 - The term that has been used historically to classify people through characteristics that stereotype and define subjects in such a way that they determine their membership in a specific group, not to mention that each day is recognized and identified within a group.

It is framed as the capacity of people to imagine and explain some daily life that results from the obvious.

Continuing in the line of the imaginary conceptualization, Jacques Lacan from psychoanalysis proposes three concepts,:

1- The real;

2 - The symbolic and

3- The imaginary that are part of the imaginary.

This leads to represent a triad, where he highlights that the real is intangible, since if this could materialize, the essence of its existence is lost, putting language as an example, when referring to the symbolic it encloses it as the basis of the set of social rules and the imaginary reflects it as a mirror stage.

The conceptual journey of the imagery is intended to define its concept and its contribution to the identification of the social imagery, which build the world and define it from the different historical modes, as it in turn welcomes and certain processes are obviated giving rise to segregation and discrimination and for this reason, "social imagery governs the processes of identification and social integration and makes social invisibility visible.

It is the way they live and are located according to a context, their purpose is to shape a reality, without mentioning that this is an absolute truth, they allow us to visualize ourselves through phrases, of individual or collective conceptions, which are permeating over time and are transformed according to realities.

Individual imaginary

Fear is built with real and imaginary components, but in the end all fear is an individual and social symbolic construction.

The link with the real-objective is never only real, our link is always ideal, in the sense that it is a cultural construction that we make and with which we read and reconstruct what comes to us from reality and this can be called representation (Weber; Durkheim) or ideology (Althusser).

This construction is the social representation of reality that we make ourselves and with which we read the real (Moscovici).

The representation of fear is social on the one hand because it is collective, that is, it arises between individuals and has in the end, the individuals themselves as a destination, but does not correspond to one or the other, but is common to a specific society.

And, in a more relevant way, it is social because it is the product of the interaction of different actors, that is, it is not created or lived by a single actor, but a multiplicity of

actors that in their exchanges of information pregnant with prejudices and deformations, create a result, a notion, which guides the behaviour of individuals.

Various processes and actors intervene in this process of building the social representation of fear. Some correspond to the real lived by the subject and another to the real symbolized by other actors.

Processes:

Victimization

The most immediate way of building fear is having been the victim of a credible threat or an act of violence itself. In this case, fear is based on the person's singular experience and can produce significant psychological damage.

Post-traumatic situations generate very large panic and inhibition behaviours that enter the strictly individual field.

By victimization it is understood as the both direct aggression, which the person suffers in his own body, and indirect, which occurs when the individual is an eyewitness to a violent act on another person.

In both cases the experience is direct and produces specific damages that translate into the individual construction of fear in any of its forms and intensities.

Vivid victimization

With this name we include that violence that we do not directly suffer or observe in person, but that makes us equally victims because they have suffered people close or distant, but that produce an effect of empathy on us and make us share the pain and anger that we know or we assume in the other.

That event that the other has suffered comes to us as a story that is produced by various types of social actors and that has different means to send us information. I would say there are three privileged types of receiving stories:

The three versions

1- The personal story.

This is the version that makes the event directly involved, the victimized. They tell what they suffered and categorize the events, the people involved, the circumstances of place and time and the reasons.

In this case, the real happens through the symbolization that the direct actors do and the way in which they represent themselves and others in history.

The knowledge of the real events is from the best source, but its reconstruction has the biases of the representation of itself and of the aggressor, his motives, feelings, social classification, that the victims make.

2 - The rumour

The second way the stories are spread is from the version made by the second actor, the one who has heard the story directly from the victims, and tells what he or she was told.

That is, there is a new version of the event that rebuilds the second actor, and then modifies a third actor, and so on.

3 - The public news

A third mechanism to construct the narrative of violence is given by the news that is broadcast by the social media, the written press, radio or television.

What journalists do is take the stories of three actors, the two mentioned above: the victims and the relatives or friends whom the victims may have told, and of the officials of the police organizations who have, in addition to the versions of the two previous actors their own observation of the place and information from other sources.

This information is processed by the media, that is, by journalists and information managers, and they are assigned a singular importance and treatment according to their professional criteria, but also in accordance with their own social representations as members of that group.

The impact of the media is one more version of vicarious victimization, only that the personal account can be offered to dozens of people, the rumour to hundreds and the news can reach thousands or millions.

But the ability to disseminate the news does not make it have a very different process from the story or the rumour, because in all cases what happens is a process.

Social fear is not built then not on real violence, but on the social representations that have made violence victims, rumours and the media.

V

The real consequences of fear

But regardless of its founded or fantasized origins, fear has real consequences. In sociology we know that something may not be true, but if people living in that situation believe it to be true, it will be true in its consequences.

That is, people will undertake or give up on their endeavours as if what they believe is true. Therefore the authenticity of its true origins loses relevance in the face of the subjective belief of its plausibility. This is what happens with the fear of violence. The

People act guided by the fear built on urban stories by friends, neighbours or the media.

Conclusion

The media are a fundamental factor in the process of expansion of fear created on social representations.

The media are privileged actors, but some more in the process of building these social representations, victims, families and friends, and the friends of the friends who told them ... also intervene. The citizens who are informed and have opinions on the subject.

The mechanisms for transforming content, the processes of re-meaning that occur with information, are part of the very constitution of communicational action that always occurs in societies, are an essential part of social life and it is not possible to claim cut them off without causing serious damage to the freedom of people.

There is no society where one lives only on truth or science, one lives on tales and fantasies, on religions and myths, on the enchantments that individuals' minds and cultures produce on the real.

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